

Genetic Diversity in Open Pollinated Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*) Germplasm

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Abstract

Information regarding genetic diversity of the base population from which potential parents are to be selected is important as it measures variance in terms of total divergence. Keeping this in mind, the present investigation was conducted in a CRBD with three replications in *Rabi* 2019 at Jalandhar, Punjab. The D^2 analysis was conducted on 20 genotypes of open pollinated spinach grouped them into seven clusters. It was concluded that one of the parents in a hybridization programme can be selected from cluster VII and other parent can be selected from cluster IV which had highest inter cluster distance from cluster VII. Cluster VII and cluster IV together covered most of the traits with respect to high cluster mean therefore, superior hybrid or transgressive progenies can be obtained from such a combination of parents.

Objectives

- To study genetic diversity among the genotypes under Jalandhar, Punjab conditions
- To identify potential parents for a hybridization programme

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References

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Introduction

Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.) also known as palak, is one of the most nutritious vegetable consumed throughout the world. Being a cross pollinated, breeding programme of this crop would mostly involve developing high yielding hybrids for which potential parents with wide genetic base should be identified.

More diverse parents show high heterosis as compared to the closely related strains. D^2 analysis is one of the most commonly used multivariate methods of analysing genetic diversity. It assists in selecting appropriate parents for a breeding programme through a precise comparison among all the variables of a population and the quantitative assessment of diversity.

Materials and Methods

Experiment was carried out at Experimental Farm of Department of Agricultural science, DAV University Jalandhar , Punja in *Rabi* 2019-20 in a CRBD with three replications. Twenty open pollinated soinach varieties taken for the study were genotypes Green star, Palak Harit Shobha, Super All Green, Evergreen, Supriya, All Green, Palak Harita, Komal Spinach, Palak All Green, Spinach Solan and Harit. Observations were recorded on ten quantitaive traits namely, days to emergence, leaf length (cm), leaf width (cm), petiole length (cm), petiole diameter (mm), number of leaves per plant, leaf area (cm²), days to first cutting, first cutting yield (g) and days to bolt.

Data were collected on five randomly chosen plants and was subjected to D^2 analysis as per Mahalanobis (1936). Using D^2 values, different genotypes were grouped into various clusters following by Tocher method as suggested by Rao (1952).

Conclusion

One of the parents in a hybridization programme can be selected from cluster VII and other from cluster IV which had highest inter cluster distance from cluster VII; together they covered most of the traits with respect to high cluster mean also therefore, superior hybrid or transgressive progenies can be obtained from such a combination of parents.

Result and Discussion

The D^2 analysis grouped 20 genotypes into seven clusters. On the basis of D^2 analysis, 20 genotypes were grouped into seven clusters. Cluster VI was the largest cluster having seven genotypes viz., All Green Composite, Pusa Harit, Local Selection 2, Local Selection 1, Spinach Solan Harit, All Green and Super All Green. Second largest Cluster I had four genotypes i.e., Supriya, Evergreen, Palak Harita and Green Flavour followed by cluster VII which had three genotypes namely, Local Selection 3, Palak Beej and Spinach Green Hara Sona. Cluster II (Samag Star and Palak All Green) and V (Ananya Green and Komal Spinach) had two genotype each while, Cluster III and cluster IV had only one genotype Palak Harit Shobha and Green Star, respectively. Members of cluster I were superior in terms of maximum number of traits followed by cluster III. Cluster VII was superior to other clusters for maximum number of traits and had highest inter cluster distance indicating the presence of highly diverse genotypes in it.

Reddy *et al.*, (2014) in Indian spinach and Sabaghnia *et al.*, (2015) in *Spinacia oleracea* also used clustering techniques to find the diversity in the genotypes and deciding the parents for future breeding programmes.

Cluster Dendrogram

